

The use of Autonomous subsurface drones and devices to enhance port security.

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Abstract — In today's global landscape, ports face multifaceted threats, ranging from terrorism to the smuggling of illegal goods like drugs and weaponry and of trafficking or illegal immigrants. In addition to traditional surface vessels, illegal operations use underwater and semisubmersible vehicles, posing challenges for conventional surveillance methods. Cameras provide limited capability for detecting underwater threats and small surface vessels. This underscores the importance of exploring alternative approaches, such as sonars, to bolster port protection and ensure comprehensive security measures.

Complex port environments require numerous or mobile sensors to ensure that no blind spots compromise security measures, resulting in a highly sensor-intensive operation. Conventionally, this requires a substantial workforce of sonar operators to manage and interpret the vast amount of data generated. To address this challenge and optimize operational efficiency, integrating artificial intelligence (AI) techniques becomes imperative. AI algorithms for interpreting sonar information may aid port security in identifying potential threats swiftly and accurately amidst the complexity of underwater environments.

Our proposed approach involves deploying single hydrophones strategically throughout the port area to automatically detect passing vessels. This data is then passed to an AI system that, combined with other sources of information, such as AIS, assesses the potential threat level. In instances where a potential threat is identified, an aerial drone is deployed to the vessel location, and captures images of the vessel, which are promptly relayed back to the AI system for further classification and evaluation. This integrated system aims to streamline port security operations, enabling proactive threat detection and response through the seamless integration of sensor technology and AI.

A demonstration of the system will be tested during the user case work package in the EU Horizon Europe project, Smaug, addressing solutions to enhance the security challenges European ports have.

1 Introduction

Maritime security is a critical concern in modern times, with increasing threats from smuggling of drugs [1] **Error! Reference source not found.** and weapons, human trafficking, and sabotage [3]. Ports, harbors, seabed infrastructure and shipping lanes are particularly vulnerable due to the high volume of traffic and the challenges of monitoring large areas with diverse vessel types and behaviors. Identifying suspicious or non-compliant vessels is vital to ensure safety and security while minimizing disruption to lawful maritime operations.

Today, maritime surveillance relies heavily on technologies like radar, AIS, and optical imaging systems, - all focusing on the above-surface picture. However, emerging threats also include subsurface vessels that will remain undetected by these systems [1][3]. Additionally, AIS provides information about a vessel's identity, location, and intentions, but can be deliberately falsified or turned off by those attempting to avoid detection [4].

Integration of multiple sensing modalities and advanced analytics is still in its early stages, leaving gaps in effectively identifying suspicious activities. To address these challenges, the EU-Horizon Europe funded project Smaug [5] proposes a suite of technologies, including hydrophone arrays for acoustic detection, deep learning for pattern recognition, UAVs equipped with high-resolution optical and infrared cameras, and multi-modal AI systems for data fusion and classification. These technologies offer complementary capabilities, combining the ability to detect acoustic signatures, correlate them with AIS data, and provide visual verification. The fusion of data from multiple sensors enhances the system's accuracy, reliability, and ability to operate in various environmental conditions.

In a technology demonstration in the port of Drammen, a

subset of the Smaug system will be demonstrated. A set of hydrophones are employed to create an acoustic trip wire detection system capable of detecting and classifying vessels based on their acoustic signatures. These classifications are cross-referenced with AIS data to identify discrepancies or suspicious patterns. When necessary, UAVs are deployed for further inspection, capturing detailed imagery in both optical and infrared spectra. The data from all sensors is fused using AI-driven multi-modal classification, and any remaining suspicious vessels are escalated to human decision-makers for final assessment. This layered and integrated approach ensures robust detection, classification, and decision-making in maritime security operations. The proposed system will be demonstrated in a test case set in Drammen, Norway, in June 2026.

2 Technology demonstration

Port of Drammen (fig 1) is a commercial port in the southeastern part of Norway, located in the end of a narrow fjord. This fjord has a very narrow area making it a natural choke point on the sailing into port of Drammen (Svelvikrenna) (fig 2). The demonstration of our research will be conducted in this choke point due to its shallowness (around 13 meters) and narrowness (less than 200 meters). These conditions will reduce the challenges with multiple targets to identify.

Figure 1 Map of the inlet to the port of Drammen.

The user case is a scenario where Port of Drammen has a heightened security alert due to loading of military equipment and personnel for a NATO deployment. The initial phase of the scenario will include a a demonstration of our approach, see Table 1.

Action	Technical remarks
MS xxxxx is moored in Drammen harbour ready to embark military vehicles and equipment.	System operational in Svelvikrenna.
Hydrophones picks up vessel sounds. Classified as a bulk cargo ship. Sound compared with AIS data and arrival notices and confirms the identity.	System must detect the sound, compare it with database to identify type. Identification is compared with AIS data and arrival notices.
Hydrophones picks up vessel sound, Classified pleasure craft. No corresponding AIS track. UAV deploys for closer inspection.	System must detect the sound, compare it with database to identify type. Compared with AIS data /arrival notices. Trigger launch of the UAV to conduct closer look.
UAV flies over the vessel and identify it as a cabin cruiser. Control centre is notified.	System must detect the vessel, compare image and other characteristics with databases to identify the vessel. Trigger notification to control centre.
Hydrophones picks up vessel sound and classifies it as unknown. The AIS track corresponding to position shows a coastal freighter. The system deploys the UAV for closer inspection.	System must detect the sound, compare it with database to identify type. With an unknown identification the system trigger UAV automatically to conduct closer inspection.
UAV flies over the vessel and a identify the vessel as coastal freighter, but the	System must detect the vessel, compare image and other characteristics with

vessel is flagged as suspicious due to former ports of call and notifications from customs. Alarm raised to control centre. USV deploys for a closer inspection of the vessels hull, no anomalies found.	databases to identify the vessel. Deploy the USV for a closer inspection of hull (surface and subsurface) Trigger correct notification to control centre.
Hydrophones picks up vessel sound classifies unknown. No matching AIS track, UAV is deployed who find no vessel, flag this as suspicious activity.	System must go through the whole protocol and end up flagging unknown.
Alarm is raised in the control centre. Security personnel take over the responsibility of the operation against the flagged vessel.	When order is given to the system, it must initiate search in accordance with given threat and deploy the necessary assets.

Table 1 A step-by-step description of the test case in Drammen port.

The proposed system to be tested in the above demonstration combines hydrophone, AIS, and camera data to determine whether a passing vessel is suspicious. The flowchart (Figure 2) shows the steps of the overall method.

The acoustic trip wire detection system employs an array of hydrophones to detect passing vessels using logistic regression [7] on a combination of narrowband, broadband [8], and DEMON [9] data. Beamforming or time-delay of arrival measurements are used to give a rough estimate of the target position.

Advanced deep learning algorithms are applied to spectrograms generated from the acoustic data, enabling real-time classification of vessel types based on their acoustic signatures.

Simultaneously, the system logs Automatic Identification System (AIS) (figure 3) data to cross-reference with the acoustic detections. By comparing the AIS-reported positions, identities, and vessel types with the classified acoustic signatures, discrepancies are flagged. Suspicious behavior, such as vessels faking their AIS signals or failing to transmit any AIS data, triggers further investigation.

Figure 3 Visualization of AIS data.

When a vessel is deemed suspicious, an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) equipped with high-resolution optical and infrared cameras is tasked to visually inspect the vessel. The UAV collects imagery and video, providing additional observational data to assess the vessel's activity and legitimacy. Image-based deep learning methods are applied on the data to determine the vessel type.

The collected data from the hydrophones, AIS, and UAV are then subjected to multi-modal classification by an AI system. If the vessel remains flagged as suspicious after this process, aggregated information from all sensor inputs is forwarded to a human decision maker. This individual assesses the situation and determines the appropriate course of action, ensuring that potential threats are addressed efficiently and effectively.

3 Discussion

The Smaug system aims to monitor ports for threats across all domains: aerial, surface, and subsurface. Extending to the underwater domain necessitates the use of acoustic sensors, as electromagnetic spectrum sensors are ineffective below the surface. By utilizing hydrophones, the system also gains an additional capability for detecting surface vessels.

While the detection and classification of vessels based on their underwater signatures have been employed for a century, these systems are typically military and rely on classified databases, as information source, for AI training or highly skilled human operators. The Smaug system proposes a low-cost, deployable, and automated solution that can be transported and set up in various locations. This makes it feasible for small and medium-sized ports with infrequent traffic to secure its area of potentially illegal or threatening operations.

Initial tests of hydrophone measurements for passing vessels indicate detection ranges of a few hundred meters for single hydrophones. Additionally, the port soundscape is generally complex, with numerous vessels passing at any given time, making it challenging to isolate a single vessel without using large hydrophone arrays.

The project is developing algorithms to manage these complex conditions. The Drammen port test case offers a unique approach to addressing this complexity by utilizing a chokepoint at the port's inlet. This ensures that all passing vessels are within the hydrophone sensors' coverage and that traffic is limited.

The proposed solution uses deep learning algorithms for target classification, which require extensive measurements of both threat and non-threat vessels. So far, the development has utilized the openly available ShipsEar dataset, but plans include conducting multi-hydrophone measurements in the ports of Valencia, Horten, and Svelvik to increase data diversity. Early classification is crucial for distinguishing between various signal types and identifying potential threats or points of interest in an aquatic environment. However, it is important to note that this initial classification focuses on a basic and rapid differentiation of detected targets, enabling the system to respond efficiently to any potentially relevant objects.

4 Summary

An automated system that employs a combination of AIS, acoustic and optical sensors for monitoring a chokepoint along the sea lane to the Norwegian port, Drammen is proposed.

AI-based detection and classification solutions are used for each sensor. Based on the combined information, an AI determines whether a passing vessel should be flagged. Aggregated sensor data on flagged vessels are passed on to the decision makers for review and as basis for their decisions for a course of action.

The system is proposed as a low-cost alternative for ship lane monitoring. Although, we expect performances inferior to state-of-the-art military systems, such a system may be a useful addition to traditional harbour security systems to provide some coverage in the underwater domain, as well as a redundancy measure for monitoring surface traffic.

The next steps will focus on gathering more extensive real-world data, using ad-hoc hardware for comparison. A Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) scheme will be implemented to improve target localisation, with exploration of various algorithms to estimate target positions using the acoustic data. The deep learning classification models require further training with larger and more diverse datasets to increase accuracy, especially in complex environments. New methods to improve signal processing for detection may also be considered.

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Figure 2 Flow chart showing the steps of the proposed method.

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